

PREPREGGING AND MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF CNT-CFRP HYBRID COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY

Epoxy-based carbon fibre reinforced composites (CFRPs), with and without carbon nanotubes (CNTs), were prepared through a solventless prepegging process; studies were conducted to optimise the material and process parameters and evaluate the curing behaviour. The CNT-CFRP hybrid composites with 0.5wt% CNTs exhibited significant improvements in interlaminar shear and torsional shear properties.

Keywords: hybrid composites, prepreg, CFRP, carbon nanotubes, torsion, mechanical properties, interlaminar shear strength

1. INTRODUCTION

Carbon nanotubes (CNTs) possess exceptional mechanical, electrical and thermal properties, making them ideal fillers for polymer nanocomposites for various structural and functional applications [1,2]. Factors influencing the properties of CNT nanocomposites have been extensively studied and the development of nanocomposites with much improved mechanical and functional properties have been reported [3-5]. Incorporation of CNTs into a polymer matrix along with long fibre reinforcements to produce hybrid composites has also attracted significant attention in recent years. The mechanical and fracture properties were improved after addition of small quantities of carbon nanotubes to the matrix [6,7]. It is also well established that the quality of composite components depends on the processing route adopted for fabrication. The aspect of producing CNT-CFRP has not been given due attention.

This paper is part of a larger project aimed at developing CNT containing CFRP hybrid composites for specialty applications. The epoxy-based CNT-CFRP hybrid composites are prepared through prepegging, a well established step in the processing of composites for high end structural applications. The prepreg manufacturing involves, i) alignment of continuous fibre bundles or tows in the longitudinal direction, ii) continuous wetting, or impregnation, of tows using a polymer resin by passing them through a resin bath, iii) maintaining the uniform thickness of resin using a device called the doctor blade, and iv) collecting the impregnated fibres on a take-up spool. The characteristics of the prepreps are a very uniform quality with consistent properties throughout due to the consistent thickness and very few voids. In this study, special focus has been placed on studying the effects of resin type and CNT content on various critical parameters in a solventless prepegging

process and on the changes in curing behaviour of epoxy and prepreg. Important mechanical properties, such as strength and modulus, interlaminar shear strength and torsional shear properties of the resulting hybrid composites were evaluated. These are significant, especially for structural applications, like specialty sports goods and the main body of wind turbine blades.

2. EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Materials and Preparation of CNT Modified Matrices

The multiwalled carbon nanotubes (NK-50 supplied by Nanokarbon, Korea) used in this work were of bamboo-like structure and were produced by a vapor grown method. The outer diameters ranged between 40-60nm and the lengths were about 20µm. Typical TEM images of these CNTs are presented in Fig. 1. Two different epoxy resins were used to study the rheological behaviours; one (EP1) was made from Epon 828 (supplied by Shell), a DGEBA epoxy, and the other (EP2) was Araldite LY556 (supplied by Huntsman), a reaction product of bisphenol A (epichlorohydrin). The carbon fiber roving (Pyrofil TR 30S, supplied by Mitsubishi Rayon, Japan) with a filament count of 6K was used as the main reinforcement. Araldite LY556 resin system was eventually selected for making prepreps, which was composed of Araldite LY556, Aradur 5021 and hardener XB 3471 (all supplied by Huntsman), which were mixed in the ratio of 100:25:12 parts by weight.

Both pristine and functionalised CNTs were employed in this work. The functionalisation method was a combination of processes chosen based on extensive studies reported previously [3-5]. The CNTs were first subjected to oxidation in a UV/O₃ chamber (Jelight 144AX-220) for 30 min, followed by treatment with a surfactant. A nonionic surfactant, polyoxyethylene phenyl ether (Triton X-100, supplied by VWR international, UK) with the critical micelle concentrations (CMC) value of 0.2mM at 25°C was used to treat the CNTs to improve the dispersion in the resin. The procedure adopted for the treatment was basically similar to that reported previously [5]. A desired amount of CNT was dispersed in acetone containing 10CMC of surfactant, equivalent to a Triton weight to acetone volume ratios of approximately 12.5 mg/1000 ml. The mixture was subjected to sonication in a bath (Branson 150) for 120 min. A desired amount of epoxy (EP1 or EP2), heated to 75°C to lower the resin viscosity, was added into the suspension of as-treated CNT/acetone to obtain 0.5wt% or 1.0 wt% CNT in the epoxy matrix. The initial dispersion was achieved by ultrasonication at 60 °C for 30min, followed by degassing in a vacuum oven at 70°C overnight to ensure complete removal of acetone. The dispersion of CNTs was further improved by mixing for 30 min using a high speed shear mixer (Ross) [4]. Two different speeds, 3000 and 4000 rpm, were used to study their effects on dispersion and viscosity of the suspensions.

Fig. 1. TEM micrographs showing morphologies of CNTs

2.2 Rheological Studies and Curing Behaviour

Rheological studies were carried out to select a suitable matrix material and identify optimal prepregging parameters. Three types of resin blends containing 0wt%, 0.5wt% and 1.0wt% CNT were prepared with both epoxy resins. The viscosity changes were measured on an oscillatory rheometer (TA 300, TA instrument) using a parallel plate geometry (with 40mm flat plate and 300 μm in gap) was used of this purpose. The effects of shear mixing speed, type of epoxy and CNT functionalisation were evaluated on the viscosity changes. Temperature sweep was also carried out for the finally chosen resin system to determine a suitable temperature for the prepreg process; the viscosity measurements were taken over a temperature range from room temperature to 50°C. Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) analysis was conducted on CNT nanocomposites as well as hybrid composite prepregs to determine the curing behaviours.

2.3 Prepreg Process and Composite Fabrication

CNT-CFRP hybrid composite prepregs were prepared on a lab-scale prepregger (Model 40 Research Tool Corp., USA). A photograph and a schematic of the prepregger system are presented in Fig. 2. Based on the outcome of the rheological studies, the temperature of the resin bath was set at 37°C, which was optimised to maintain the viscosity of the CNT-resin mixture within the required limits (15~20 Pa s) and to achieve good wetting of the carbon fibre tow. The flattening pins and dies were also maintained at the same temperature. Various combinations of line speed and exit die gap were tried to control the resin content in the prepreg. Prepregs were prepared with a consistent resin mass fractions of 60±5%.

2.4 Fabrication of Specimens and Mechanical Tests

The flexural properties and the interlaminar shear strength (ILSS) of the hybrid composites were determined according to the specifications, ASTM standards D790 and D2344, respectively. 2.5 mm thick laminates consisting of 9 layers of unidirectional prepregs [0]₉ were fabricated by hand lay-up and curing in a vacuum hot press at 90°C for 8 hours. Specimens of 12.7 mm wide x 70 mm long were cut from the cured composite plates.

Specimens for the ILSS were cut from a 5mm thick unidirectional laminate, $[0]_{18}$, prepared and cured by same method.

Fig.2. Photograph showing lab scale Prepregger (b) Schematic of prepregger

In-Plane shear moduli of the hybrid composites were determined using tubular specimens with a length of 100 mm and internal and external diameters of 6 ± 0.2 mm and 10 ± 0.2 mm, respectively, as shown in Fig. 3. Specimens were fabricated by wrapping eight unidirectional, 90-degree, layers of prepreg over a Teflon rod, which were then pressed in an outer mould consisting of identical two halves with internal longitudinal grooves with a diameter of 10.5 mm. The tubes were wrapped with vacuum bags along with porous peel plies and breeder, which were then cured as described in the previous section; ends of composite specimens were bonded into aluminium tubes as the fixtures for gripping, Fig. 3, according to the specification, Standard MIT-STD-375 (ASTM D5448). A gauge section length of 60 mm was obtained after fixing. Two pairs of uniaxial strain gauges were bonded in a “fish bone” manner, each placed on the opposite sides near the two ends of the tubes. The specimens with the end tabs were gripped on a universal testing machine (Instron Model 1125) and loaded at an angular velocity of 0.05 rad/min. At least three specimens were tested for each set of conditions.

Fig.3. Torsional shear specimens and test set-up.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

3.1 Rheological Properties

3.1.1. Effects of CNT Content and Mixing Speed on Viscosity

Viscosity is the single most critical parameter for processing of preregs. It must fall within certain limits (1.5~ 2.4 Pa s) for processability and good wetting of fibres. A series of experiments was conducted to identify optimal processing conditions with improved CNT dispersion while maintaining the viscosity within the limits. Several important parameters, such as the effects of CNT content, mixing speed, type of epoxy and CNT functionalisation, were evaluated.

Fig.4. shows the variation of viscosity as a function of the shear rate of untreated CNTs dispersed in an epoxy (EP1) using a high speed mixer at 3000rpm. The viscosity of the suspension was consistently higher for the nanocomposites than for the neat epoxy, and it consistently increased with increasing CNT content [8,9]. The overall responses of the CNT nanocomposites were similar to that of the neat epoxy in terms of the Newtonian behaviour. However, small decreases in viscosity with increasing shear speed were observed for all materials studied. This observation was well expected due to shear thinning, which is in turn caused by localised shear-induced heating and a small decrease in aggregate size [8].

Fig. 4: Effects of CNT content and shear rate on viscosities of resins with and without untreated CNTs.

Fig. 5: Variation of viscosity of untreated 0.5wt% CNT/EP1 suspension as a function of shear rate showing the effects of mixing speed.

The viscosities measured for the 0.5wt% untreated CNT/epoxy suspension after mixing at a higher speed of 4000rpm are presented in Fig. 5. A significant reduction in viscosity was noticed when a higher mixing speed was used, indicating the efficiency of high speed shearing in breaking up the CNT aggregates. This is further confirmed by the optical microscope images of the CNT/epoxy suspensions, containing different CNT contents and after dispersion at different mixing speeds, as shown in Fig. 6. The aggregates of different sizes are clearly seen depending upon the processing parameters used: the aggregate size grew with increasing CNT content, and it was the largest for the 1.0wt% CNTs/epoxy suspension. Mixing at a higher speed significantly improved the dispersion with smaller aggregate sizes, thus further studies were made below using high speed mixing.

Fig. 6: Dispersion state of untreated CNTs in epoxy matrix (EP1):(a) 0.3wt% CNT/epoxy ; (b) 0.5wt% CNT/epoxy; (c) 1.0wt% CNT/epoxy mixed at 3000rpm; and (d) 0.5wt% CNTs/epoxy mixed at 4000rpm

3.1.2. Effects of Epoxy Type and CNT Functionalisation on Viscosity

To further study the effects of epoxy type, both untreated and functionalised CNTs were dispersed in the EP2 resin system using the same procedure and dispersion speed of 4000rpm. Fig. 7(a) shows the variation of viscosity for different materials. It should be noted that the EP2 resin system without CNT has a lower viscosity (9.8 Pa s) than the EP1 resin (10.8 Pa s), so were the corresponding nanocomposite suspension containing 0.5wt% untreated CNTs (Fig. 7a).

To evaluate the effects of functionalisation, 0.5wt% CNTs functionalised by a surfactant were dispersed in EP2 resin based on the same procedure. A further reduction in

viscosity was observed compared to the CNT/EP2 nanocomposite suspension (Fig 7b). The effects of surfactant treatment on viscosity of nanocomposite suspension were significant, the viscosity was decreased to 10.7 Pa s at a low shear rate and increasing the shear rate did not much reduce the difference. The improved dispersion quality of CNTs in the epoxy matrix was mainly responsible for the lowered viscosity [10], confirming the importance of functionalisation of CNT reinforcements for processability of prepregs. Triton is a nonionic surfactant that has functional groups containing hydrophilic as well as hydrophobic segments. The hydrophobic octyl group of the surfactant interacted with CNT through adsorption while the hydrophilic segment could link with epoxy through hydrogen bonding [5] resulting in improvement of CNT dispersion.

Fig.7. Variation of viscosity of 0.5wt% CNT/epoxy suspensions as a function of shear rate: (a) effects of type of resin; and (b) effect of CNT functionalisation

3.1.3. Temperature Sweeps

To identify the most suitable temperature for prepregging without adding any solvent, a temperature sweep was performed on the mixtures after blending with hardeners and the results are shown in Fig. 8. The viscosity of neat EP2 resin dropped significantly (from 9.8 Pa s to 4.2 Pa s) after a hardener was added mainly because of the inherently low viscosity of the hardener used (a mixture of Aradur 5021 and hardener XB 3403). It is interesting to note that the differences in viscosity of the neat resin and CNT modified resins were gradually reduced by employing a temperature slightly higher than ambient. Based on the information obtained from the temperature-dependent viscosity curves in Fig. 8, 37 °C was chosen for prepreg fabrication.

3.2 Thermomechanical Properties and Curing Behaviours

3.2.1 Curing Behaviours of Neat and CNT Modified Resins

Various studies reported that CNTs could act as a catalyst for epoxies and initiate early stage curing [11, 12]. A large decrease in activation energy is not very desirable for a prepreg process as this may shorten the process time available for making prepregs and

decrease the shelf life of prepregs. Therefore, the effects of CNT addition on curing the behaviour of epoxy were evaluated using the dynamic differential scanning calorimetry (DSC). The DSC thermograms of the neat epoxy and nanocomposites obtained at a ramping rate of 10°C/min are given in Fig. 9, and important kinetic parameters determined from these curves are given in Table 1. The thermograms of neat epoxy and CNT nanocomposites exhibited two exothermic peaks [13], representing two curing reactions, which were well expected as the resin system used (Araldite LY556, Aradur 5021 and hardener XB 34) contained a co-curing agent in addition to the main hardener. The main exothermic peaks for both the neat resin and the CNT nanocomposites started at the same temperature, about 131°C (Table 1). The exothermic peak for the 1.0wt% CNT/epoxy was marginally lower than the neat epoxy or 0.5wt% CNT/epoxy, indicating catalytic behaviour for nanocomposites with a high CNT content. The heat of reaction (ΔH) for the neat epoxy and the 0.5wt% CNT nanocomposite was also marginally higher than that for the 1.0wt% CNT nanocomposite, suggesting a reduction in the degree of cure. It is envisaged that the presence of a large amount of CNT nanoparticles physically hindered the mobility of the polymer chains and the cross linking process [12]. To further study the curing reaction mechanisms and any possible catalytic effect of CNTs, the fractional extent of conversion of nanocomposites are plotted against temperature as shown in Fig. 9b. S-shaped curves were obtained for all materials studied regardless of CNT addition, confirming that the autocatalytic curing kinetics remained unchanged even with the addition of CNTs [9].

Fig.8: Effect of temperature variation on viscosities of epoxy resins with and without CNT incorporation

3.2.2 Curing Behaviour of Prepregs

The thermomechanical characteristics of the uncured CNT-CFRP composite prepregs were also investigated based on the dynamic DSC analysis with the same experimental conditions. The curing parameters determined from the thermograms are given in Table 2. A trend similar to the curing behaviour of was observed; the 1.0wt% CNT-CFRP composite prepreg exhibited a lower curing onset temperature, T_{onset} , a lower peak temperature, T_p , and a lower heat of reaction, ΔH , than the neat CFRP and 0.5wt% CNT-CFRP hybrid composite prepregs. The activation energy, E_a , was determined according to the specification, ASTM E698-5, to evaluate the presence of autocatalytic kinetics [14]. The variation of exothermic peaks in response to varying ramp rates of 5, 10 and 20°C/min

were recorded. The activation energies were calculated from the slope obtained by plotting \log_{10} (heating rates) against the inverse of corresponding peak temperatures ($1/T_p$) and are presented in Fig. 10a. As expected, the E_a values decreased consistently with increasing CNT content (Table 2) as a reflection of increased catalytic effect because of carbon nanotubes. The glass transition temperatures, T_g , were measured from the DSC thermograms of the prepregs cured at 90 °C for 8 hours as shown in Fig. 10b.

Fig.9 Dynamic DSC thermograms of curing for neat epoxy and CNT nanocomposites: (a) plot of heat flow; and (b) Extent of conversion as a function of temperature

Table 1: Effects of CNT content on onset temperature, T_{onset} , peak temperature, T_p , time to peak temperature, t_p and heat of reaction, ΔH

Sample	T_{onset} (°C)	T_p (°C)	t_p (min)	ΔH (J/g)
Epoxy	131	144.0	1.26	262
0.5wt% CNT/epoxy	131	143.6	1.24	261
1.0wt% CNT/epoxy	131	143.2	1.19	254

Both CNT-CFRP hybrid composites showed a lower T_g than the neat CFRP without CNTs, where the reduction was significant for the hybrid composites containing 1.0wt% CNT as a result of a lower degree of cure. The physical hindrance of CNTs and CNT agglomerates impaired the mobility of the active groups in epoxy and the curing agent, leading to lack of curing and requiring a longer post-cure time for the 1.0wt% CNT-CFRP hybrid composites.

3.3. Mechanical Properties of Hybrid Composites

3.3.1 Flexural Test

The flexural properties of CFRP and CNT-CFRP hybrid composites are shown in Fig. 11. Since the carbon fibre content, stacking sequence and curing parameters were all kept the

same, the changes in flexural properties of CFRP should be directly related to the matrix properties which were influenced by the dispersion and content of CNTs. With in the data scattering, both the flexural strength and modulus increased marginally with the addition of 0.5wt% CNT. This was expected because the epoxy matrix contained well dispersed, functionalised CNTs. A further increase in CNT content to 1.0wt% however, was rather detrimental to the flexural strength and modulus, most probably due to potential agglomeration of CNTs a high content of CNTs.

Table 2: Effects of CNT addition on onset temperature, T_{onset} , peak temperature, T_p , time to peak temperature, t_p , heat of reaction, ΔH , activation energy, E_a and glass transition temperature, T_g , for CFRP preregs with and without CNTs.

Sample	T_{onset} ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	T_p ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	t_p (min)	ΔH (J/g)	E_a (KJ/mol)	T_g ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)
CFRP prepeg	136	151.1	1.17	182.3	82.2	114.3
0.5% CNT/CFRP prepeg	136	150.1	1.15	174.1	80.7	112.8
1.0% CNT/CFRP prepeg	135	149.0	1.11	153.2	78.0	104.4

Fig.10. Plot of Log (heating rate) vs. peak temperature for uncured preregs; (b) thermograms of cured CFRP composite preregs obtained at a heating rate of $10^0\text{C}/\text{min}$.

Fig11. Flexural Properties of CNT-CFRP hybrid composites as a function of CNT content

3.3.2 Interlaminar Shear Strength and In-Plane Shear Modulus

The interlaminar shear strengths (ILSS) of CFRP and CNT- CFRP hybrid composites were measured using the short beam specimens and the results are shown in Figure 12a. The ILSS increased by 11% with the addition of 0.5% CNT, but it decreased with a further increase in CNT content to 1.0wt%. It is suspected that the tendency of agglomeration of CNTs at a high content was mainly responsible.

The shear modulus was measured by torsional loading of the tubular specimens. Torsional rigidity is considered one of the most important characteristics of many specialty structural composite components, such as golf shafts and turbine blades for wind mills. The test and specimen geometry is found particularly useful for obtaining reliable data where a low variation in the measured values is of paramount importance [15]. The shear modulus values presented in Fig. 12b show a trend similar to the ILSS against the CNT content with the highest value corresponding to about 0.5wt% CNTs. The improvements in torsional modulus against the neat CFRP were 18% and 11% respectively for the 0.5wt% and 1.0wt% CNT contents.

Fig. 12: Shear properties of CNT-CFRP hybrid composites.

To understand the mechanisms responsible for enhancement of interlaminar shear strength for CNT-CFRP hybrid, the fracture surfaces of the ILSS specimens were examined and the images are shown in Fig. 13. The matrix in the neat CFRP composites was completely

separated from the fibre surfaces, indicating weak interfacial adhesion, and debonding was a primary mode of failure in these composites. On the other hands, a large portion of the fibre matrix interface was intact even after fracture for the composites containing 0.5wt% CNTs. The matrix material exhibited shear lips, an indication of significant plastic deformation and strong interfacial adhesion as a result of CNT incorporation [16].

Fig.16. SEM micrographs of the fracture surface of short beam shear test specimens: CFRP composites made from (a) neat epoxy and (b) epoxy containing 0.5wt% CNTs.

4. CONCLUDING REMARKS

Epoxy-based carbon fibre reinforced composites (CFRPs), with and without carbon nanotubes (CNTs), were prepared through a prepreg process. The influence of CNT content on different prepreg processing parameters, rheological behaviours and cure behaviour of epoxy resins and CFRP composites were evaluated. Mechanical properties that are directly relevant to practical applications of CNT-CFRP hybrid composites were characterised. The following can be highlighted from the study.

1. The viscosity of epoxy resin increased with increasing CNT content. A higher speed shear mixing and functionalisation of CNT are beneficial to lowering the viscosity of the CNTs nanocomposites.
2. The temperature sweep indicated that the effects of viscosity difference between the CNT modified and neat epoxies could be minimised by employing a temperature slightly higher than ambient. Based on the findings obtained from the rheological studies, suitable processing parameters were chosen for lab-scale production of CFRP prepregs.
3. The effects of triton treated carbon nanotubes on the cure behaviour of epoxy and prepreg were studied with dynamic differential scanning calorimetry.

The catalytic activity of surfactant treated CNTs was negligible at 0.5wt% CNT as indicated by a lack of change in the initial curing. The catalytic activity became prominent when the CNT content was increased to 1.0wt%. The degree of cure was lower for the prepreg containing 1.0wt% CNT than for the other materials.

4. The interlaminar shear strength and torsional modulus of the 0.5wt% CNT-CFRP hybrid composites increased by 11% and 24%, respectively, compared with the neat CFRP composites, as an indication of the improved properties of the matrix material. The flexural strength and modulus of the hybrid composites also showed marginal improvements against the neat CFRP laminates.

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